

Research

Optimization of path planning for automatic atomized spraying equipment for high-speed railway based on vision

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Liaoning, 116021 China**How to cite this article:**Author, Zeyang He, Jianguo Li, Mingjian Lu, Zijian He, Xiaoyu Wang (2025). Optimization of path planning for automatic atomized spraying equipment for high-speed railway based on vision. North American Academic Research, 8(4), 171-181. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15252345>**Abstract**

To enhance the spraying efficiency and effectiveness of robots, the effects of trajectory planning using polynomial interpolation functions with 3, 5, and 7 segments in the joint space were analyzed for the robotic arm. By comparing the trajectory curves under different indicators, the construction of a "5-7-5" segmented polynomial function was proposed. The final simulation curves of the robotic arm's joint position, velocity, and acceleration showed continuous smoothness without abrupt changes and had good convexity. Furthermore, an improved particle swarm optimization algorithm was used to optimize the optimal trajectory at time t , adjusting dynamic inertia weight coefficients and adaptive learning factors to improve the optimization performance and rapid convergence of the particle swarm. The results showed that the total planning time before improvement was $T=9.4746s$, while after improvement, it was $T=6.3758s$, reducing the total time optimized by $3.0988s$, with an overall improvement of 49% in time optimization, demonstrating a significant enhancement in optimization effectiveness.

Keywords: 5-7-5 segmented polynomial function; improved particle swarm algorithm; dynamic inertia weight coefficient; adaptive learning factor

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Introduction

As the high-speed rail industry develops, the quality requirements for surface coating of carriages have increased. Atomizing spray, as a critical step, affects the aesthetics, durability, and lifespan of the carriage^{[1][2]}. Traditional manual spraying is labor-intensive, with issues such as unstable quality and material waste, making it unable to meet current needs; thus, developing automated spraying equipment is of great significance^{[3][4]}. In industrial manufacturing, visual technology offers opportunities for path planning in automated spraying equipment. It can accurately obtain shape and position information of the high-speed rail carriage surface, which is used for path planning in atomizing spray on complex-shaped carriages, such as visual cameras collecting point cloud data of workpieces^[5], providing a foundation for generating spraying trajectories. However, the unique structure of high-speed rail carriages, their large size, complex curved surfaces, and strict coating standards pose challenges to path planning for visual-based automated spraying equipment. Although there are studies on automatic spraying path planning in industrial coating, few focus on the scenario of high-speed rail atomizing spray^{[4][5]}.

Path planning is a core technology in automatic spraying equipment. Proper planning can improve efficiency, ensure uniform coating, and reduce idle travel and paint waste^[6]. Early path planning methods based on geometric models, such as equal offset method and circular cutting method, struggled to adapt to the complex curved surfaces of high-speed rail car bodies^[7]. With the development of intelligent algorithms, genetic algorithms have been used for spray path planning due to their strong global search capabilities and good robustness^{[8][9]}, but traditional genetic algorithms tend to fall into local optima and converge slowly. Current path planning algorithms struggle to balance spraying efficiency and coating quality when dealing with the complex curved surfaces of high-speed rail, and they inadequately consider the special process requirements for atomic gray spraying^[10].

This study aims to combine the advantages of visual technology with the special needs of high-speed rail atom gray spraying, deeply explore the path planning problem of automatic high-speed rail atom gray spraying equipment based on vision, develop efficient, accurate and reliable path planning scheme, improve the quality and efficiency of painting, and provide technical support for the development of high-speed rail manufacturing industry.

Figure.1 Experimental Platform of Special Robot Putty Spraying System

Three-dimensional reconstruction of the surface of the vehicle body through the visual system

In this study, the visual system provides a three-dimensional reconstruction of the vehicle body, thus laying the foundation for path planning. As the core sensing device, LiDAR rapidly emits a large number of laser beams onto the side wall surface of the high-speed train. After reflection, by measuring the time delay between emission and reception of the laser, and based on the principle that the speed of light is constant, the distance to the reflection points on the side wall surface can be accurately calculated. These distance data form a 3D point cloud, which can precisely reflect the overall contour of the side wall, millimeter-level welding protrusions or depressions, and even minor scratches.

1. Point cloud processing method

After acquiring massive point cloud data, the LiDAR vision system initiates an intelligent feature extraction program. Using edge detection algorithms, it accurately locates the side wall edges, capable of precisely outlining both straight and curved lines. At the same time, planar fitting algorithms are used to identify planar regions on the side wall surface. The original point cloud data contains noisy points and outliers, which interfere with subsequent analysis. The vision system first applies Gaussian filtering and median filtering algorithms. Gaussian filtering averages weighted by neighboring points, smoothing the data and removing random noise; median filtering replaces points with the median of their neighbors, effectively eliminating pulse noise and other anomalies. After filtering, the point cloud data becomes more realistic and reliable^[11].

2. Point cloud feature extraction

Edge Feature Extraction: The visual system uses edge detection algorithms to identify the edges of the high-speed rail side walls. This algorithm calculates the gradient intensity and direction at each point in the point cloud data, identifying areas with significant gradient changes. These areas often correspond to the edges of the side walls, such as where they connect with other components. Accurate edge extraction clearly defines the boundaries of the side walls, providing crucial boundary information for subsequent model construction and path planning.

Planar Feature Extraction: The Planar Consistency (RANSAC) algorithm is used to identify planes. The RANSAC algorithm randomly selects a set of points, assuming they form a plane, and then calculates the distances from other

points to this plane. Based on the distance threshold, it determines whether these points belong to the plane^[11]. After multiple iterations, the plane model containing the most points is found, thus extracting the planar regions of the side wall surface. These planar features are crucial for determining the spray path and angle of the spray gun in flat areas.

Curvature Feature Extraction: To calculate the curvature of the side wall surface, the visual system constructs a local coordinate system based on point cloud data and estimates the curvature by calculating the second derivatives of the point cloud in this local coordinate system. Areas with higher curvature are typically the corners or complex curved sections of the side walls. During painting, special path planning is required for these areas, such as reducing the spray gun's movement speed and adjusting the painting angle, to ensure a uniform coating.

3. Model construction and optimization

Based on various features extracted, the visual system constructs a 3D model of the high-speed rail side wall. During the construction process, methods such as triangular meshes are used to reconstruct the surface of the model, converting discrete point cloud data into continuous geometric models. At the same time, optimization algorithms like least squares are employed to adjust the constructed model, making it more closely match the actual shape of the side wall. The optimized model not only includes the geometric shape information of the side wall but also integrates characteristics related to painting processes, such as area and curvature in different regions, providing a precise foundation for path planning^[12].

Robot spray trajectory planning

When the robotic arm performs a predetermined spraying task, its path must remain smooth and free of abrupt changes to ensure stable operation and minimize vibrations, thus avoiding premature wear due to excessive friction [13]. Therefore, it is essential to pre-plan the movement trajectories of each joint in the robotic arm, ensuring that the displacement, velocity, and acceleration paths are all smooth and without abrupt changes. This approach minimizes the impact of sudden shocks on the robotic arm, enabling it to complete the spraying task smoothly and accurately [14].

The trajectory planning of robotic arms includes joint space trajectory planning and Cartesian space trajectory planning. When planning trajectories in Cartesian space, the end-effector motion trajectory is first planned according to requirements, then the end-effector trajectory is mapped to joint space through inverse kinematics to obtain the motion trajectories of each joint. However, this method involves a large amount of computation, may fail to reach certain intermediate points, and has singularities that could lead to loss of joint speed control.

Joint space trajectory planning involves designing a joint motion path from the starting point through intermediate points to reach the target point. When performing trajectory planning in joint space, if the given conditions are posed in Cartesian space, it is necessary to first use inverse kinematics to convert the path points from Cartesian space to joint space. This method is simple and timesaving, as it only requires considering joint angle displacement, velocity, and acceleration, with no singularity issues. To simplify the calculation and control of trajectory planning and tracking for robotic arms, trajectory planning is chosen to be performed in joint space [15].

Joint space trajectory planning

1. "5-7-5" polynomial trajectory planning

Through the simulation results of MATLAB and the study on joint space trajectory planning using existing cubic, quintic, and haptic polynomials, it was found that If a single polynomial trajectory planning method is used [16], it is difficult to achieve continuous control of joint speed or acceleration, leading to severe vibrations during the spraying process of the robotic arm, consuming a large amount of energy, and reducing the work efficiency and service life of the robotic arm [17]. Therefore, this section adopts the "5-7-5" segmented polynomial trajectory planning method to interpolate the motion trajectory of the robotic arm. This method satisfies all constraint conditions while integrating the advantages of cubic, quintic, and haptic polynomials, avoiding their respective drawbacks, ensuring the continuous smoothness of the joint position, speed, and acceleration curves, and reducing computational load while improving convexity. Overall, the "5-7-5" segmented polynomial trajectory planning is a method that combines the interpolation of quintic and haptic polynomials [18]. Specifically, it consists of three stages: the first stage uses quintic polynomial interpolation from 0t to 1t; the second stage uses haptic polynomial interpolation from 1t to 2t; the third stage again uses quintic polynomial interpolation from 2t to 3t. The interpolated polynomial is:

$$\begin{cases} \theta_{i1}(t) = a_{i15}t^5 + a_{i14}t^4 + a_{i13}t^3 + a_{i12}t^2 + a_{i11}t + a_{i10} \\ \theta_{i2}(t) = a_{i27}t^7 + a_{i26}t^6 + a_{i25}t^5 + a_{i24}t^4 + a_{i23}t^3 + a_{i22}t^2 + a_{i21}t + a_{i20} \\ \theta_{i3}(t) = a_{i35}t^5 + a_{i34}t^4 + a_{i33}t^3 + a_{i32}t^2 + a_{i31}t + a_{i30} \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

In the formula, $i=1,2,3,\dots,n$ represents the joint a_{i21} a_{i11} code a_{i31} ; and respectively represent the n-th coefficient of the first, second and third interpolation functions of the i-th joint.

During the movement of the robotic arm, four path points θ_{i0} θ_{i1} are θ_{i2} θ_{i3} set:,,, and, which represent the joint

angles at each path point. Each curve segment has its own position, velocity, and acceleration constraints. Typically, the initial and final points have zero velocity and acceleration. The curves passing through these points are continuous. Therefore, there are 20 unknowns and 20 constraints that can be simplified into the following matrix form:

$$A \cdot a = q \tag{3.2}$$

Among them, A is a 20x20 constraint matrix about the time variable, and only related to the time t, a is a 20x1 coefficient matrix to be solved, q is a 20x1 joint Angle matrix, which is known.

$$q = [0 \quad 0 \quad \theta_{i3} \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad \theta_{i2} \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad 0 \quad \theta_{i1} \quad \theta_{i0} \quad 0]$$

$$a = [A_1 \quad A_2 \quad A_3]^T$$

$$\begin{cases} A_1 = a_{i15} + a_{i14} + a_{i13} + a_{i12} + a_{i11} + a_{i10} \\ A_2 = a_{i27} + a_{i26} + a_{i25} + a_{i24} + a_{i23} + a_{i22} + a_{i21} + a_{i20} \\ A_3 = a_{i35} + a_{i34} + a_{i33} + a_{i32} + a_{i31} + a_{i30} \end{cases} \tag{3.3}$$

Then the coefficient matrix a can be expressed as:

$$a = A^{-1} * q = [A_1 \quad A_2 \quad A_3]^T \tag{3.4}$$

2. Simulation of "5-7-5" segmented polynomial trajectory planning

To verify the effectiveness of "5-7-5" segmented polynomial trajectory planning, simulation analysis is carried out in MATLAB using the six joints of a 6-degree-of-freedom robotic arm as an example. The optimal trajectory and optimal time are solved by the standard particle swarm algorithm, which is then compared with the improved particle swarm algorithm in the next section.

The joint angles corresponding to the four path points of the robot arm are shown in Table 1:

Table.1 Joint Angle

Path points	joint	joint	joint	joint	joint	joint
	1(rad)	2(rad)	3(rad)	4(rad)	5(rad)	6(rad)
1	0.0000	0.7532	0.0000	0.2343	0.0000	0.7532
2	0.0000	0.7532	0.0000	0.6073	0.4983	0.6073
3	0.7532	1.0325	0.2343	0.4983	0.7532	0.4983
4	0.6073	0.2932	0.4983	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000

Set the population size of the particle swarm to 20, and limit the maximum number of iterations to N=20. Additionally, set c_1 the inertia weight c_2 coefficient ω to 0.65, the individual learning factor to 0.5, and the swarm learning factor to 0.6. The velocity and acceleration change ranges are specified to be within [-4, 4]. Through the simulation process, we can obtain the joint position, velocity, and acceleration change curves obtained using the standard particle swarm "5-7-5" segmented polynomial trajectory planning method. As shown in Figures 1, 2, and 3.

Figure.2 Variation Curves of First and Second Axes

Figure.3 Variation Curves of Third and Fourth Axes

Figure.4 Variation Curves of Fifth and Sixth Axes

From the above figure, it can be seen that using the "5-7-5" segmented polynomial, the joints of the robotic arm can plan a continuous, smooth, and mutation-free trajectory while satisfying all constraint conditions. Additionally, using a seventh-degree polynomial for the intermediate segment also achieves good convexity effects. However, due to the use of standard particle swarm optimization over time, the parameters are relatively fixed, leading to longer computation times and slower convergence rates of fitness. Therefore, we need to improve this aspect to optimize the planning time.

Time optimal trajectory optimization based on improved particle swarm

By employing the "5-7-5" segmented polynomial, we can achieve a relatively ideal trajectory. However, although the position, velocity, and acceleration function curves planned largely achieve continuity and controllability, the lack of constraints on the kinematic parameters at each moment in the interpolated trajectory prevents us from ensuring that the total path time is minimized. Therefore, based on the standard particle swarm optimization algorithm, we conducted a single-objective optimization [19] for time t . First, we dynamically adjusted the inertia weight and learning factor to enhance the optimization performance and rapid convergence of the particle swarm. Next, we comprehensively considered the time consumed by each segment of the trajectory to determine the overall optimal time. Finally, we obtained the optimal trajectory of the robotic arm under the condition of optimal time.

1. Dynamic decreasing inertial weight

Using a fixed inertia weight ω can easily lead to local optima during the solution process. Considering that algorithms are influenced by different inertia weight coefficients in both global and local optimization, dynamic decaying inertia weights are introduced to balance the interaction between search speed and search accuracy, achieving a dynamic equilibrium point [20], as shown in the formula.

$$\omega = \begin{cases} \omega_{\max} - (\omega_{\max} - \omega_{\min}) \cdot \left(\frac{k}{N}\right)^2, & f \leq f_{avg} \\ \omega_{\max}, & f \geq f_{avg} \end{cases} \quad (4.1)$$

Among them ω_{\max} , ω_{\min} and are the preset maximum and minimum inertia weight coefficients, typically set to 0.9 and 0.4, respectively; N is the maximum number of iterations; k is the current iteration count. In this way, the inertia weight decreases gradually as the number of iterations increases, maintaining high global search capability in the early stages of the algorithm, while shifting towards stronger local search capabilities later on to enhance the likelihood of finding the global optimal solution.

2. Dynamic learning factor

To improve the search ability and accelerate the convergence speed of particles and groups, the learning factor is dynamically adjusted by combining it with the number of iterations in the current generation, and the communication between particles and populations is increased. The function expression is shown as follows:

$$\begin{cases} c_1 = c_{\max} - (c_{\max} - c_{\min}) \cdot \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi}{2} * \frac{k}{N}\right) \\ c_2 = c_{\min} + (c_{\max} - c_{\min}) \cdot \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi}{2} \cdot \frac{k}{N}\right) \end{cases} \quad (4.2)$$

Among them c_{\max} , c_{\min} represents the maximum value and represents the minimum value. In the initial stage, particles are in a self-learning phase c_1 , requiring enhanced individual learning capabilities; therefore, the local learning factor has a higher value, but the convergence speed is relatively slow. As the number c_2 of iterations c_1 increases, to improve overall convergence speed and achieve a global optimal solution, it is necessary to enhance the group's learning capabilities; thus, the global learning factor needs to be gradually increased while the value is gradually reduced, with the range set at [0.2, 4][21].

3. Optimal particle update and optimal time

After the iterative update is completed, the optimal velocity and position of the updated particle are obtained to obtain the final optimal particle:

$$\begin{cases} v_{id}^{k+1} = \omega v_{id}^k + c_1 r_1 (p_{id} - x_{id}^k) + c_2 r_2 (p_{gd} - x_{id}^k) \\ x_{id}^{k+1} = x_{id}^k + v_{id}^{k+1} \end{cases} \quad (4.3)$$

The expression represents the component of the i-th particle in the d-dimensional direction during the k-th iteration. v_{id} represents the velocity of the particle p_{gd} , x represents the displacement of the particle, represents the optimal component of the current position of the particle, and represents the optimal component of the overall particle population.

Through the above improvements, we can get the optimal time for each segment of each joint:

$$f(t) = \min \sum_{i=0}^n (t_{i1} + t_{i2} + t_{i3}) \quad (4.4)$$

Trajectory planning optimization simulation experiment and analysis

Through the analysis of the improved particle swarm optimization strategy, we maintain the constraints and planned path points of the robotic arm while ensuring the effectiveness of the experimental comparison. The population size, maximum number of iterations, and velocity and acceleration c_2 c_1 limits of the particle swarm remain unchanged. On this basis, we set the decaying range of the inertia weight from 0.9 to 0.4 and adjust the sum of the dynamic learning factors, expanding its adjustment range from a minimum of 0.5 to a maximum of 2[22]. Through MATLAB simulation experiments, we can obtain the optimized optimal fitness curve, as shown in the figure:

Figure.5 Fitness Curve before Optimization

Figure.6 Optimal Fitness Curve after Optimization

The comparison reveals that the optimized particle swarm algorithm achieves a faster convergence rate. After 12 iterations, all joints of the 6R robotic arm have reached their optimal positions, and the planning time for each joint has been significantly reduced. In contrast, before optimization, the particle swarm algorithm was still in the learning adaptation phase at this point, consuming a substantial amount of time. Additionally, due to the single-objective optimization of the planning time t , the trajectory segments spent by the planned robotic arm traversing the path points are noticeably shorter [23], as shown in Figure 6.7:

Figure.7 Manipulator Traversal Waypoints before Optimization

Figure.8 Manipulator Traversal Waypoints after Optimization

After adopting the improved particle swarm optimization algorithm, significant improvements were achieved in the "5-7-5" segmented polynomial over each time period. Before optimization, the maximum running times for each joint in the three stages were: $t_1=2.1631$ for the first stage, $t_2=4.8012$ for the second stage, and $t_3= 2.5103$ for the third stage, with a total time $T=t_1 + t_2 + t_3 = 9.4746$. After time optimization, the times became $t_1=1.9836$ for the first stage, $t_2=1.1274$ for the second stage, and $t_3=2.2648$ for the third stage, with a total time $T=t_1 + t_2 + t_3 = 6.3758$. The total planning time was reduced by 3.0988. The change curves of each joint after improvement are shown in Figures 8, 9, and 10.

Figure.9 Variation Curves of First and Second Axes after Improvement

Figure.10 Variation Curves of Third and Fourth Axes after Improvement

Figure.11 Variation Curves of Fifth and Sixth Axes after Improvement

From the above figure, it can be seen that under the premise of meeting all constraints and ensuring smooth, continuous, and non-sudden position, velocity, and acceleration curves with good convexity, the improved trajectory planning optimization method significantly reduced the operation time of the robotic arm from 9.4746 seconds to 6.3758 seconds, optimizing the overall time by about 49%, effectively improving the work efficiency of the robotic arm. This indicates that using the improved particle swarm algorithm for "5-7-5" segmented polynomial trajectory planning of the robotic arm is feasible. This method not only reduces the planning time but also enables high-quality, high-precision, and efficient completion of spray planning tasks, playing a crucial role in subsequent research.

Conclusion

When mobile robots operate on large multi-dimensional tasks, the precision of the robotic arm's trajectory planning and work efficiency significantly impact task effectiveness. To enhance both aspects, this study optimizes the trajectory planning algorithm for the robotic arm's joint space. The research analyzes the influence of various polynomial interpolation functions on the position, velocity, and acceleration curves of the trajectory, selecting the "5-7-5" segmented polynomial as the core method. Using the standard particle swarm optimization algorithm on the MATLAB platform, although it produced the expected curve, the algorithm was time-consuming and affected efficiency. Therefore, the standard particle swarm optimization algorithm is specifically improved by dynamically adjusting the inertia weight and learning factor, enhancing the algorithm's optimization capability and improving convergence speed.

The simulation and comparison experiments have verified that the time optimal trajectory planning method is feasible and has significant advantages, and the improved algorithm has better practical application effect. These improvements ensure that the robot arm spraying trajectory is smooth and continuous during the operation of the mobile robot, which provides support for its efficient and accurate task completion.

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